

THE EVALUATION OF INTERNAL STRESSES IN A SHORT FIBRE METAL MATRIX
COMPOSITE BY NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

P.J. Withers*, D. Juul Jensen**, H. Lilholt** and W.M. Stobbs*

* Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy
Pembroke Street, Cambridge, CB2 3QZ, U.K.

** Metallurgy Department
Risø National Laboratory
Roskilde, Denmark

ABSTRACT

The use of neutron diffraction is described for the evaluation of the mean matrix and fibre strains in a short fibre metal matrix composite as a function of its thermal history. The data obtained are analysed in terms of a developed Eshelby based model for the stresses generated as a result of the different thermal expansion coefficients and compliances of the two phases. The results are discussed in terms of the partial diffusional relaxation which can occur as a function of temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Dual phase engineering materials, as exemplified by the SiC/Al short fibre metal matrix composite system (SFMMC), are typically inhomogeneously stressed as a result of their fabrication and service history because of the different values of the thermal expansion coefficients, elastic constants and relative ductility of the fibres and matrix. The evaluation of the internal stress distribution is of importance in determining the mechanical properties of a SFMMC and neutron diffraction techniques are well suited for this purpose through the characterisation of the mean matrix and fibre strains in such a system. This is both because neutron diffraction methods sample volumes orders of magnitude larger than a typical deformation volume for such a system, and because it is the mean strains which determine both the uniform and the locally fluctuating components of the internal stress distributions. The locally fluctuating stress can be determined from the mean matrix and fibre strains provided the relationship between them is well understood. Thus we have developed Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method [1,2] to model the SFMMC. Such a model inevitably oversimplifies the complex inherent triaxial stress state and necessarily requires that the short fibres be treated as ellipsoids. Furthermore the model, as treated here, neglects relaxation processes so that in comparing experimental data with predictions of the theory we are inherently examining the extent to which relaxation is important.

We describe here the development and use of the Eshelby treatment for the interpretation of the neutron diffraction data obtained for a model SFMMC of nearly pure Al containing 5% by volume SiC fibres. Our aim has

been to understand the effects of a typical fabrication history and of subsequent thermal treatments.

MATERIALS AND THE METHOD OF STRAIN MEASUREMENT

The Al/SiC SFMMC was fabricated by a conventional powder metallurgy route, comprising blending, cold compaction, hot pressing (at 550°C), hot extrusion (at 500°C) and furnace cooling. The Al powder (5-10 micron R400 ALCOA) has a natural surface layer of Al_2O_3 which becomes a 1 vol% dispersion of Al_2O_3 particles in the final material; these serve to make the microstructure more thermally stable than pure Al. The matrix is otherwise largely free from complicating precipitates and solid solutions (unlike Al2124, Al6061 etc). The SiC fibres (Tokawhiskers-Sumitomo Corp.) were mainly cubic, but contained (111) microtwins and a small proportion of faulted hexagonal polytypes [3]. The (111) whiskers were ~1 μ m in diameter with a volume averaged aspect ratio (l/d) of ~5 in the final composite, which exhibited a moderate degree of alignment with the extrusion direction.

A conventional triple axis spectrometer at the Risø DR3 reactor was used for the strain measurements, and a graphite monochromator crystal allowed the selection of a neutron wavelength of 0.308 nm from the incident continuous wavelength spectrum. The samples were placed in special sample holders with the extrusion direction either horizontal and bisecting the angle between the incident and the diffracted beam, or vertical. The longitudinal and the transverse components of the strain could thus be determined using Bragg's Law. The stress free lattice plane spacings were taken from measurements on the pure matrix and on free fibres. The background to the method has been described by Allen et al. [4].

Figure 1. Two Al(111) diffraction peaks measured in situ at 300°C for planes perpendicular to the extrusion direction.

A small quartz vacuum furnace was attached to the neutron spectrometer for work at elevated temperatures, within which the samples were surrounded by a Ta heating element allowing typical heating rates, to temperatures below 500°C, of 25°C/min. The furnace gives rise to a slightly increased background level but does not change the sample peak position or the peak shape.

Examples of measured diffraction peaks for the longitudinal (111) Al lattice spacing are shown in figure 1, as fitted to Gaussian functions using a least squares fitting routine. These measurements were obtained for two samples at 300°C with and without SiC fibres. The peak for the composite is shifted by 0.2° relative to that for the matrix material, corresponding to a compressive strain of 20×10^{-4} . Strains of -1.2×10^{-4} could be evaluated.

MODELLING A SFMMC

A simple model for a SFMMC treats the system as comprising perfectly aligned prolate spheroids of a single major to minor axis ratio (equal to the fibre aspect ratio), placed randomly in an isotropic matrix. For such a system, Eshelby's method of 'equivalent homogeneous inclusions' [1,2] provides an analytic solution for the mean matrix strain. For the high volume fractions typical of metal matrix composites the approach must be modified so that the inclusions sample the mean stress [5,6].

For a free body, with no externally applied surface tractions;

$$(1-f)\langle\sigma\rangle_M + f\langle\sigma\rangle_F = 0 \quad \text{Eqn (1)}$$

where f is the fibre volume fraction and $\langle\sigma\rangle_M$ and $\langle\sigma\rangle_F$ are the mean matrix and mean fibre stress vectors respectively. M (Bold symbols denote either 6x6 tensors or 6x1 row or column vectors.)

Here we have taken $\langle\sigma\rangle_F$ to be the stress given by Eshelby except that the inclusion samples (especially for large f) the mean matrix stress;

$$\text{i.e. } \langle\sigma\rangle^F = C_M(e^C - e^T + \langle e \rangle_M) \quad \text{Eqn (2)}$$

$$= C_F(e^C - e^{T*} + \langle e \rangle_M) \quad \text{Eqn (3)}$$

Where C_M and C_F are respectively the matrix and fibre elastic compliances (these are given in the appendix) e^C , e^T , e^{T*} are the constrained strain, the equivalent homogeneous stress free transformation strain and the stress free transformation strain of the real inclusion respectively as given by Eshelby.

$\langle e \rangle_M$ is the mean matrix strain where; $\langle\sigma\rangle_M = C_M \langle e \rangle_M$.

The constrained strain is defined by the relation

$$e^C = S e^T$$

S being a function of the ellipsoidal geometry [1].

From the equation of stress balance (Eqn 1);

$$\langle \mathbf{e} \rangle_M = -f(\mathbf{e}^C - \mathbf{e}^T) = -f(\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{e}^T \quad \text{Eqn (4)}$$

Substituting Eqn(4) into Eqns.(2) and (3) gives:

$$\langle \mathbf{e} \rangle_M = f(\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) [(\mathbf{C}_M - \mathbf{C}_F)(\mathbf{S} - f(\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})) - \mathbf{C}_M]^{-1} \mathbf{C}_F \mathbf{e}^{T*} \quad \text{Eqn (5)}$$

from which the mean matrix strain can be calculated from the stress free transformation strain (\mathbf{e}^{T*}). The form of the transformation strain for thermal residual stress is given in the appendix.

The elastic anisotropy of the fibres (assuming transverse isotropy) can be included through the compliance tensor \mathbf{C}_F (see appendix). The anisotropy of the matrix compliance is more difficult to deal with; the model, for example, becomes non-analytic. However it seems reasonable to assume that, on average, the fibres experience a matrix with the elastic properties of polycrystalline aluminium. Neutron diffraction samples only those specific diffracting planes which satisfy the Bragg equation at a given specimen orientation. Thus, in order to relate two measurements of matrix strains in a given direction using different lattice reflections, the differing stiffnesses of the matrix for these crystal directions must be considered. Using a Reuss model [8] the specific lattice strains (\mathbf{e}_{hkl}) can be converted to an equivalent strain \mathbf{e}_e ;

$$\mathbf{e}_e = \mathbf{e}_{hkl} \times (E_{hkl}/E_{poly})$$

It is these \mathbf{e}_e strain values which can be compared with the model matrix strains.

We show respectively in figures 2a and b the longitudinal and transverse strains for the fibres and matrix as predicted for the temperature drops specified, on the assumption of no stress relaxation. The families of lines are for fibre aspect ratios (1/d) of 20,5,2, and 1 and a volume fraction of 5%. Young's modulus (E_{111}) is exceptionally high for SiC in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction, so that the longitudinal fibre strain predicted by the anisotropic model is smaller than that which would be expected on an isotropic fibre model. Perhaps more importantly, one finds that the inclusion of fibre anisotropy into the model predicts an increase in the matrix strains. Hence the fibre anisotropy increases the local stresses around the fibre in a real composite so that decohesion might be expected at lower applied stresses than if the fibres were isotropic.

DISCUSSION

The data we discuss here were obtained for a range of thermal treatments, and are shown plotted in figures 2a and b. As-received specimens of the composite were annealed for five hours at 500°C and then further annealed at 400°, 300°, 200° and 150° for periods of 1 hour, 3 hours, 8 hours and 8 hours respectively, prior to a water quench. Subsequently after a further relaxation period of one day at room temperature the fibre and matrix mean strains were evaluated by the method described above. The observed fibre aspect ratio was about 5, as volume averaged, so that within the experimental errors involved, the predicted stress balance (eqn 1) between the fibres and matrix is followed reasonably

Figure 2. The curves predict the variation of (a) mean fibre and (b) mean matrix strain with temperature drop longitudinal and transverse to the extrusion direction. The experimental fibre and matrix strains obtained after one day at R.T. are shown for the temperature from which the specimen was quenched. The \square data were obtained immediately upon cooling for the specimen heated in situ (fig.3), the \downarrow in fig.2b indicates the change after 8 hrs. Longitudinal strains for the 'as-received' specimens are represented by horizontal lines. This emphasises that the 'equivalent temperature' can be inferred from the graph.

well. This indicates the validity of the two phase model overall. It is thus interesting that whatever the annealing treatment, the observed strain state appears to be consistent with a temperature drop from an equivalent temperature of between 220° and 250°C down to room temperature (R.T.).

This suggests that diffusional relaxation of the internal stresses is, overall, not easy though the complexity of the problem is emphasised in that the data for the as received furnace cooled material indicates an equivalent temperature of ~100-125°C. This in turn suggests that the high local stresses present after extrusion can promote diffusional relaxation, but that once these high stresses are relaxed further diffusional relaxation becomes markedly more difficult.

Figure 3. Longitudinal a) fibre and b) matrix mean strains derived from (111) lattice plane spacings measured at temperature.

Given these observations, we undertook dynamic measurements of the longitudinal lattice spacings at a series of elevated temperatures and the strains thence evaluated are shown in figures 3a and 3b. It should be emphasised that the times taken for an Al and a SiC lattice spacing measurement were 10 mins and 30 mins respectively and that relaxation with time is to be expected (and was observed). The reduction in the retained matrix tensile strain at the end of the thermal cycle after a further 8 hr rest period at R.T. is indicated in figure 3b. The strains are given with respect to the lattice spacings at temperature; these were measured for Al (see figure 4) and calculated for SiC. The errors involved are large for

Figure 4. The longitudinal Al₍₁₁₁₎ lattice plane spacings for the composite and reference alloy measured at temperature.

the Al data, because the strains are relatively smaller and the expansion coefficient larger than for SiC. Nevertheless the strain variations with temperature are qualitatively in accord with simple predictions based on thermal stress relaxation as suggested by the previous experiments. We see that as the temperature is increased the strains decrease in magnitude from their R.T. values to zero at between 60° and 130° (the 'equivalent temperature' of the as received material). They then increase numerically in a reverse sense for both phases but at a decreasing rate relative to the plots for figure 2, so that above about 250°C relaxation mechanisms dominate.

Furthermore it is interesting that the fibres and matrix retain significant elastic strains even after 2 hrs at 500°C ($T/T_m = 0.8$). The behaviour on lowering the temperature to R.T. shows strong hysteresis and now stress balance (Eqn.1) between the two phases is not followed. This is significant given that this relation was fulfilled both for the in-situ quenched specimen and for the extended rest time samples (see figure 2). The dynamically evaluated Al strains are generally larger than would be expected on the basis of our model. There are a number of reasons why this might be so. These include the variation of stress relaxation rate at fibres of different aspect ratio, but the experimental errors involved in deriving the Al strains are large (as previously noted).

A more detailed interpretation of these data will be presented elsewhere, here they illustrate why specimens quenched from different annealing temperatures exhibit similar strain states. Clearly the "equivalent temperature" does not reflect in any simple manner the temperatures at which the internal stresses were zero upon cooling.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that:

- 1) neutron diffraction can be used to provide evaluations of the mean matrix and fibre strains in a SFMMC sufficiently accurately to discuss predictions of the stress distribution as a function of thermal history.
- 2) the strain measurements obtained at room temperature for the fibres and matrix are consistent with the stress balances predicted by the developed Eshelby model.
- 3) considerable but not total thermal relaxation can occur over a period of hours even at room temperature. By contrast, relatively high mean strains can be retained for considerable periods at much higher temperatures.
- 4) the concept of the 'equivalent temperature' usefully represents the residual internal stress state of the SFMMC at R.T., however it does not indicate the temperature at which the matrix and fibres were unstrained.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described was carried out both at the University of Cambridge and at Risø, Denmark and we are grateful for the provision of facilities to Prof. D. Hull and Dr. N. Hansen whom we also thank for helpful advice. P.J. Withers acknowledges the Risø National Lab. for financial support. We also thank P. Nielsen for the composite specimens fabricated at Risø.

REFERENCES

1. Eshelby, J.D., Proc. Roy. Soc. 1957, 241A, 376
2. Eshelby, J.D., Proc. Roy. Soc. 1959, 252A, 561
3. Nutt, S.R., J. Am. Cer. Soc. 1984, 67, 428
4. Allen, A.J., Hutchings, M.T. and Windsor, C.G., Advances in Physics 1985, 34, 445
5. Tanaka, K. and Mori, T., Acta Metall. 1970, 18, 931
6. Pederson, O.B., Fundamentals of Deformation and Fracture, Proc. IUTAM, 1984, Eds. K.J. Miller, B. Bilby, Pub. CUP 1985
7. Takao, Y. and Taya, M., J. Appl. Mech. 1985, 52, 806
8. Reuss, A., Z. Angew. Math. Mech. 1929, 9, 49
9. Metals Handbook, 9th Ed., Vol.2, American Soc. for Metals. 1979
10. Pandey, B.P., Dayal, B., Phys. Stat. Solid (b) 1973, 58, K53
11. Petrovic, J.J., Milewski, J.V., Rohr, D.L. and Gac, F.D., J. Mat. Sci. 1985, 20, 1167
12. Brakman, C.M., J. Appl. Cryst. 1983, 16, 325

APPENDIX

From the Metals Handbook [9] $E = 69 \text{ GP}$ and $\nu = 0.33$ for aluminium. Hence C_M is obtained with:

$$\text{for } i = 1 \text{ to } 3; \quad C_{ii} = 1.022 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$\text{for } i = 4 \text{ to } 6; \quad C_{ii} = 5.04 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$\text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3; \quad C_{ij} = 2.59 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2 \quad i \neq j$$

$$\text{Otherwise } C_{ij} = 0 \quad (\text{Repeated indices are not summed})$$

Taking SiC elastic constants which reflect the theoretical [10] and experimental measurements [11]:

$$S_{11} = 3.31 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}; \quad S_{12} = -0.87 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$$

$$S_{44} = 3.94 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$$

The anisotropic fibre compliance, C_M , is referred to the Eshelby axes with [111] along the 1 axis [12], so that:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= 5.52 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2; & C_{22} = C_{33} &= 4.45 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2; \\ C_{44} &= 4.28 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2; & C_{55} = C_{66} &= 3.70 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2; \\ C_{12} = C_{21} = C_{31} = C_{13} &= 4.44 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2; & C_{32} = C_{23} &= 1.13 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for the case of thermal stresses, the transformation strain is given in terms of the coefficients of thermal expansion of the matrix (α_M) and fibre (α_F) by:

$$\begin{aligned} e_i^{T*} &= (\alpha_M - \alpha_F)\Delta T & \text{for } i &= 1,2,3 \\ &= 0 & \text{for } i &= 4,5,6 \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_M = 23.7 \times 10^{-6}/K$ and $\alpha_F = 4.5 \times 10^{-6}/K$.